

INFINITICS: RATE CONCEPT WITHIN AN INFINITE SET

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ABSTRACT. The comparison of infinite sets, fundamentally governed by Cantorian cardinality (bijections), and another method given by Infinitics which compares two comparable infinite sets with the help of a simple graph. In this paper, we propose an alternative method, which uses Infinitics's and Cantor's method to compare two comparable infinite sets with their number of elements and with the concept of imaginary infinity/infinitesimal limit of a infinite set.

1. INTRODUCTION

Infinitics, A new branch of mathematics which specifically deals with hyperreal numbers, introduced in late 2024, gives a method where Hyperreals, specifically infinities and infinitesimals, can be easily compared and calculations with hyperreals with the help of introducing rate concept. It is true that Infinities and infinitesimals does not have a factor of rate in real life, still by considering a single infinity's rate of increasing, 'X', which happens to be equal to "undefined" in real life, in Infinitics it is considered as some random variable. Now we can compare two infinities or infinitesimals with the help of that infinity's rate, 'X' (Ratnani, 2024).

Cantor has provided a method to compare two infinite sets, by keeping the elements of two infinite sets in one-to-one correspondence and compare them (Cantor, 1891). Infinitics also gives us an alternative method, which plots comparable elements onto the graph, with the 'n'th element on the x-axis and the value on the y-axis with suitable scale for the comparison and see their slopes, greater the slope, then that infinite set has less elements than the infinite set, which has a lower slope in comparison (Ratnani, 2024). But Infinitics fails to mention anything about the number of elements in an infinite set, which is an infinite number. This paper talks about how we can apply the rate concept with any infinite sets.

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2. DISCUSSION

Applying Rate to the elements appearing in a infinite set seems very argumentative, but since, we have seen that infinitics's rate method has various applications with Hyperreals and the number of elements of a Infinite set is a 'Infinity'. Thus, we can assume the same with rate but still, in reality it's very much wrong and illogical.

From Infinitics, we know one thing that 0.999...999 with Infin having 'Z' Infin's rate and 0.999...999 with Infin having '3Z' Infin's rate, means that there are Infinitely more number of 9's difference in them. These are considered as totally different with respect to Hyperreal numbers. If you see an example of an infinite set containing all the natural numbers,

$$A = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, \dots$$

$$N(A) = 'H' \text{Infinity}$$

If you consider a infinity 'H' for this set's number of elements and if you say if we change the number the infinity 'H' into a higher infinity and say these are two infinite sets of same natural Numbers having two different number of elements, H infinity and an infinity greater than H infinity, is completely unacceptable and logically, even in Infinitics also.

Thus, an Infinite set has it's own unique number of elements and we can't assign a different infinity to it's number of elements.

By logic, the number of elements of an infinite set can never be infinitesimal nor a rational numbers with decimal points but at fractional unit time for this 'H' Infinity seems to have fractional number of elements, which is not possible. **Thus, we use unit times which are whole numbers.** Still, we can use fractional unit times depending on the need for a function or a different method.

Now, The main trick is to consider a conventional infinite set and define it's number of elements by assigning it an Infinity Variable and compare it with other Infinite sets by forming a mathematical relation between their elements.

The question is why a variable? Can't we write the actual infinity with the help of Infins? We can just write an value of some Infinity let's say 'Beta Infinity' with 'Z' Infin's rate and further compare it with Infinite sets, as There's no biggest Infinity nor smallest Infinity, so it won't be a problem but then there won't be any explanation about why we choose this Infinity, still also it won't create much problem.

In this paper, we are going to keep it in a general variable 'G'. Since, it is an infinity, let's say it's rate of Increasing be 'Y', the reason why didn't choose 'X' is that then we are applying that the Infinite set is increasing with a multiple of 10, which is the definition of 'X', that's why let it be 'Y' rate of increasing. We can let the number of elements of natural number set be 'G' for the convention.

We can also simply see the increment in their elements (only in case of increasing type of elements), in comparison as whenever one of the infinite set seems to reach any one infinite number first, then that set has less elements than the other. But there are some exceptions when they have same cardinality. The reason why we are taking any infinite number is because we can't say what's the value of the actual exact limit of any infinite set, because we can say that it's an infinity but which infinity? when we say it's A infinity and for the same set but named a different one, it's B infinity (an infinity greater than A infinity), then this second infinite set has more elements, which is a contradiction, as both are the same infinite sets. Thus, while comparing infinite sets with increasing type of elements, we should consider taking any one infinity for the comparison. Otherwise we can consider that the limit of such infinite set is some adverb 'Infinite' (∞) or the idea of infinite. In the case of decreasing type of elements, the limit is some adverb 'infinitesimal' (ϵ) or the idea of infinitesimal.

For example, if a set A contains all natural numbers and a natural number + 0.5,

$$A = 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, \dots$$

Here, the subset 1.5, 2.5, 3.5, ... has the same cardinality as the set of natural numbers. Thus, the number of elements of A is equal to twice the value of 'G' or twice the number of elements in the set of natural numbers.

$$N(A) = 2 * G'$$

If we have two infinite sets having different type of elements then we cannot do anything unless we have a relation between their infinite number of elements.

As we proved, for a given infinite set, it has its own unique number of elements which is some infinity, now for a different method to compare two infinite sets' elements in increasing or decreasing order, where the limit of the elements is either some infinitesimal or infinity, we can label each element as "element at 1st unit time, ... 2nd unit time, ... 3rd and so on. **Note that we aren't applying rate concept to the places of elements of an infinite set, but labeling them and calculating the element at infinite unit time is used to find out the 'imaginary' infinity limit that is used to compare between two infinite sets.** If that infinity is small as compared to the other, then that set has more elements compared to the other set. **Note that this is an imaginary infinity limit, it's not equal to the actual limit, which is adverb infinite (∞) or the idea of infinity.**

If we take above example and apply this method, then suppose natural number's imaginary limit is 'H' infinity and set A has imaginary limit is an infinity smaller than 'H' infinity, so therefore, as set A has smaller infinity imaginary limit, thus it has more elements than set of natural numbers, which is the same answer as above. If we have a decreasing type of infinite set, where the limit is

zero or any infinitesimal, we will see the pattern over labeled unit times elements and calculate an element at infinite unit time. In comparison whichever set's imaginary infinitesimal limit is closer to zero, then that set has less elements than the other or we can take a reciprocal of this imaginary infinitesimal limit which leads to an infinity and then we can apply the same rule of imaginary infinity limit for an infinite set and compare both.

3. CONCLUSION

Now, we can compare two infinite sets with the help of number of elements which ultimately depends on the elements by taking the set of natural numbers, \mathbb{N} , as a point of comparison whether the given infinite set is bigger than \mathbb{N} or not with the help of 'G', the rate of infinite set of natural numbers. Other method to compare two infinite sets with increasing or decreasing type of elements is by finding imaginary infinity/infinitesimal limit and compare both with the rules mentioned.

REFERENCES

- [1] Georg Cantor. On an elementary question in the theory of manifolds. In William B. Ewald, editor, *From Immanuel Kant to David Hilbert: A Source Book in the Foundations of Mathematics*, volume 2, pages 920–922. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1996. Translated by W. Ewald. Original German title: Über eine elementare Frage der Mannigfaltigkeitslehre. Original publication in *Mathematische Annalen*, vol. 46, pp. 487–492, 1895 (or sometimes cited as 1891, though the journal publication is 1895).
- [2] G. Ratnani. *Infinities: A best way to infinity*. Notion Press, 2024.